

SONNETS delivers an innovative methodological framework for public sector organisations and related stakeholders to accelerate the transformation of the public sector through the identification, analysis and take-up of emerging technologies that hold the potential to transform and infuse real value to public services.

OUR VISION

INFORMATION

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www.sonnets-project.eu

Join our Expert
Advisory Group

Atos

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SONNETS

SOCIETAL Needs ANALYSIS and
EMERGING Technologies in the public SECTOR

Transforming the public sector
into a technology and
innovation leader

IDENTIFICATION OF BARRIERS TO OVERCOME

FINANCIAL

- Shrinking public budgets
- Resources allocation processes
- Economic context
- Credit crunch & lack of VCs

LEGAL

- Complex and sometimes contradictory laws and regulations
- Corruption
- Administrative fragmentation
- Internationalization obstacles

ORGANIZATIONAL

- Risk aversion and fear of failure
- Lack of incentives and meritocracy
- Organizational silos and lack of cooperation
- Cumbersome processes and bureaucracy

POLITICAL

- Lack of political will
- Inadequate leadership
- Political instability

HUMAN CAPITAL

- Ageing workforce and lack of new recruits
- Insufficiency of IT skills
- Skills obsolescence

For further information:

<http://www.sonnets-project.eu/content/results>